

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF INTELLECTUALLY SUCCESSFUL TEENAGERS

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Abstract: In this article, today's teenager is required to increase the level of self-acceptance at the expense of personality traits, successful communication, universal qualities and appearance, in addition, the technology of "I-image" correction and deviant behavior in teenagers who are difficult to educate. behavior management system is intended to provide psychological and pedagogical support to the success of educational subjects.

Key words: teenager, pedagogue, competence, upbringing, family. Parent, referent, behavior.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the process of working with teenagers who are difficult to educate is directly related to the study and research of personality traits that affect the educational efficiency of each teenager to one degree or another. After all, the main participants of the educational process in educational institutions are students and teachers.

Today, educational institutions are the most dynamic aspect of the ever-changing continuous education system. In the content and organizational sense, it is considered as an opportunity to shape the individual educational direction of the student, and it includes probable-necessary and at the same time conditional-necessary knowledge and skills.

Difficulty in upbringing is analyzed based on the following criteria:

- low level of self-acceptance;

- low level of acceptance of others,
- manifestation of emotionality, which can be different according to its nature;
- dependence on others, i.e. externality;
- striving for superiority.

When processing the results of the socio-psychological flexibility questionnaire, data confirming the presence of signs of maladjustment among the students of general education schools were obtained. A decrease in the activity index was observed in almost all of the adolescents who participated in the study.

The study of the characteristics of the "ego" in teenagers with difficult upbringing made it possible to create a generalized psychological portrait of this category of students. Selection criteria were as follows:

- Disadaptation index in the questionnaire of socio-psychological flexibility is lower than 68 points;
- "Who I am?" non-existence of the third referent group according to the methodology (M.N. Ovchinnikova);
- "Who I am?" low level of reflexive activity according to the methodology
- "Who I am?" lack of meaning of self-acceptance and productive personality according to the methodology.

Adolescents adequately assess themselves in their current situation, accept themselves as individuals, are able to perceive themselves as possessors of positive, socially desirable characteristics, and are, in a certain sense, satisfied with themselves. At the same time, they do not always manage to adequately evaluate the results of their activities and compare themselves with others. They cannot look critically at their capabilities, they often overestimate their capabilities, especially this is evident in their attitude to studies. Many of them are characterized by an inadequate and unrealistic level of self-requirements.

The data obtained as a result of our study of the above characteristics of schoolchildren confirmed the data of other researchers.

As a result of the analysis of socio-psychological status characteristics of adolescents with difficult upbringing and their future projections, we also determined the disparity between the current status and future life prospects. Adolescents note their helplessness at the moment and do not see the possibility of this situation changing in the future, and refuse to study from the failures that may be associated with studying (that it is not necessary as an excuse), they try to avoid situations such as unwillingness to work, turning to deviant forms of behavior.

Adolescents prioritize autonomy in their relationship with their parents. And parents strive to harmonize personal and social maturity in teenagers. They do not trust teenagers, considering them unsuccessful, independent and immature, but at the same time they try to limit them from difficulties and control their behavior. Adolescents believe that their parents often reject them instead of accepting them. Striving for independence, first of all, which is manifested in the forms of behavior, the modern student of the school feels the need for support from his parents, and the lack of it is a stressor that increases personality disorder in a teenager. Therefore, the results of the survey conducted among teenagers, who are the object of our research, provide an opportunity to note the following trends in the development of family interactions with parents. First of all, teenagers feel indifferent attitude towards themselves from their parents and learn the experience of indifferent and formal interactions in the family. This may lead to self-doubt and anxiety about building a happy family life in the future. The disproportion of educational influence by parents, noted by adolescents, leads to a high level of anxiety, self-doubt, and the absence of a sense of the permanence of the environment.

It is possible that this leads to insufficient development of a sense of responsibility in adolescents, because despite the fact that they are given independence (high autonomy, low level of directiveness), adolescents do not feel strict and iron

discipline rules enough, in turn, post-violation e "They don't accept tiros enough either. All this leads to the formation of an external life position, which is manifested in the imposition of responsibility for the happenings on others. Therefore, the family as a factor affecting the lifestyle includes a wide range of socio-economic and socio-psychological aspects that cause the development of the child's personality. Among them, a special place is occupied by the personality characteristics of parents, their principles and the direction of values. The system of ideas, views and beliefs of parents is reflected in their educational activities (for example, the scope of knowledge, uniqueness of views and beliefs, ideas about the characteristics of child development and factors that determine it) and is reflected in their behavior . This has a significant impact on the formation of one or another characteristics of a teenager. Such views, imaginations and expectations of parents play an important role in communication with teenagers. The evaluation for the student society is very different from the evaluation in the family. Many teenagers have a negative attitude towards educational institutions, educational activities, as well as teachers. The study of the characteristics and levels of mental development of schoolchildren - adolescents with difficulty in upbringing showed that in most adolescents prone to maladjustment, low memory productivity, predominance of mechanical memorization, predominance of concrete and functional levels of generalization, abstract they are distinguished by insufficiently developed thinking. In addition, low level of work ability and cases of quick fatigue are characteristic of this category of teenagers. These factors are one of the reasons for insufficient formation of educational skills and qualifications. Constant difficulties in studying, often falling into the situation of failure lead to a decrease in positive motivation to study and inability to accept educational activities in these students. Of course, a sufficient level of psychological competence is required to eliminate such situations.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above, it can be said as a conclusion that in all adolescents with difficult upbringing, the insufficient development of reflexive activity is clearly noticeable. After all, today's teenager is required to increase the level of self-acceptance at the expense of personality traits, successful communication, universal qualities and appearance. In addition, the technology of correction "Embodiment of Me" and the system of managing deviant behavior in teenagers with difficulty in education provides psychological and pedagogical support for the success of educational subjects. In this process, we think that it is necessary to deeply study and analyze the circumstances related to determining the level of psychological competence of each pedagogue.

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